

Modular Multi-View AI-Based 3D Human Pose Estimation with Edge Computing

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Abstract. Single-camera human tracking struggles with complex scenarios with occlusions. Additionally, connecting multiple cameras to a central PC hinders real-time capabilities and scalability. We propose a modular multi-camera human pose estimation system powered by AI vision and edge computing. We developed an edge module for camera image acquisition, 2D human pose estimation, and publishing key pose data. One of these modules is comprised of a Jetson Orin Nano and an RGB camera. A central PC merges pose data from multiple modules to reconstruct 3D human poses. By placing 4 modules around a robotic cell we can achieve near real-time performance.

Keywords: computer vision, pose estimation, edge computing, safety, ROS

1 Introduction

The integration of robots in industrial sectors has revolutionized manufacturing and production processes by improving efficiency, precision, and safety. However, the need for advanced human-robot interaction increases as the complexity of industrial tasks rises. One key aspect for HRI is to accurately estimate human poses in 3D space. Research in 3D human pose estimation is key for safety, interaction, and learning between humans and robots. To achieve this, vision-based solutions provide great flexibility in human pose estimation, but are sensitive to light conditions and occlusions. Different technological approaches, like wearables and area scanners, are discussed in section 2.

Industrial environments can be challenging due to occlusions, changing lighting conditions, and diverse worker clothes. Multi-view approaches provide an advantage in overcoming these challenges, providing information that single-view systems lack. In this paper, we propose a modular and scalable multi-view solution enhanced by edge devices. We introduce a self-contained embedded system that handles image capture and 2D human pose inference. Each of these systems connects to a central processing unit that adapts a 3D human pose reconstruction algorithm to the number of connected devices.

2 Related Work

This research is based on developments made by Pertusa *et al.* [6] in the European Union’s Horizon Europe MERGING project. At the end of this study, it was observed that occlusions are a major obstacle for continuous and robust human tracking system in a robotic cell. The addition of cameras in the system was limited by the bandwidth of the system. Thus, an alternative that leverages edge computing was proposed, which is detailed in this research.

Alternatives for 3D human pose estimation require sensors that merge RGB cameras with depth measurements [2] or focus on single-view pose estimation. Solutions that include other technologies for human detection include wearable sensors or safety-rated monitored stop operations [1]. Current market wearables are based on inertial measurement units [3] or electromyography [7], but these approaches are intrusive for workers. Additionally, these solutions require daily maintenance and can hinder movement.

Research is also being pushed on collaborative fenceless robots. Robots that have been developed specifically for collaborative use include the iiwa from KUKA, Baxter from Rethink Robotics and YuMi robot from ABB. Mayyas *et al.* [4] detail the use of multiple laser sensors to recognize the surrounding environment of the robot and enabling the interaction process. The information about the perceived environment is used to replan robot motion, avoiding obstacles and trying to fulfill the tasks without an emergency shutdown.

3 Method

Our implementation consists of multiple edge devices dedicated to handling cameras and inferring 2D human pose, alongside a central computing unit for 2D human pose matching and 3D geometric triangulation. Each camera has been previously calibrated w.r.t one or more cameras. The communication between devices is done with a ROS2 local network. Fig 1 shows the ethernet connections and the flow of information of our proposal. By using edge devices to acquire and

Fig. 1. (a) Every device is physically connected to a PoE switch. (b) Each edge device handles one camera and sends the processed information to the central PC.

to locally process images the bandwidth of the network and load in the central PC is reduced. Instead, only a short custom message containing poses is sent.

3.1 2D Pose Estimation

A YOLOv8 human pose estimation neural network model is optimized in TensorRT to run on our devices. The inference of this model provides a list of 17 keypoints for each person in the captured images.

3.2 3D Pose Estimation

The 3D pose estimation ROS2 node developed for the central PC adapts to the number of cameras and edge devices connected. 3D pose estimation is performed in three main steps: 2D pose matching, 3D pose triangulation, and 3D pose matching.

The 2D matches between poses are optimized by an Hungarian algorithm [5]. The cameras connected to the system are iterated through in two layers, where cam_i is the current reference and cam_j is a calibrated camera against the current reference. For the current camera pair, a cost matrix $C_{A_{ij}}$ of size $k-by-l$ is built with the possible pose matches. For every pose P_k generated in cam_i and every pose P_l generated in cam_j , the aggregated pixel space Euclidean Distance for the 17 keypoints pair is calculated. This populates the $C_{A_{ij}}$ cost matrix. Once every set of poses is processed and the matrix is complete, the Hungarian algorithm selects the best matches. Since the field of view between a pair of cameras does not completely overlap, not every detected person should have a real match. This is properly handled by assigning a cost threshold to the optimization.

The 3D triangulation is performed using epipolar geometry based on the transformation matrices attained via the camera pair calibration. This reconstructs the human keypoints in homogeneous coordinates p_4 , using cam_i as the reference coordinate system. These keypoints are processed to calculate the 3D position of the human w.r.t cam_i . The result of this process is a local list of triangulated poses, T_{ij} . For the first camera pair, all new triangulations in T_{ij} are inserted into the global array of 3D poses, T . For every subsequent camera pair, new triangulations in T_{ij} are compared and matched against T . Let matrix $C_{B_{ij}}$ be the cost matrix used for analyzing the 3D Euclidean Distance between the triangulated pose P_i in array T and each new triangulation in T_{ij} . Matches are optimized with a Hungarian Algorithm and filtered based on the distance. If $cam_i \neq cam_1$, then an additional transformation is performed to T_{ij} to match the frame of reference. When a match is found, keypoints are weighted to improve the 3D pose. Once all camera pairs are processed, T is the complete set of 3D poses for all humans inside our robotic cell.

4 Experimental Results

We evaluated our proposal in a robotic cell setup, shown in Fig 2. Our setup consists of four Jetson Orin Nano 8GB, four Basler acA1920-40gc cameras, one

central PC, and one PoE switch. Each camera is mounted in a corner of our 4 meters by 4 meters robotic cell, at a height of 3 meters, and rotated to focus on the center of the cell, where an ABB robot is placed. Every device is connected to the switch, and each camera is assigned to one Jetson.

Fig. 2. Layout of the robotic cell used for testing human detection.

Each camera pair is calibrated with a 9x6 checkerboard. Considering cam_i as the reference for cam_j of a calibrated camera pair, relevant matrices are saved.

4.1 Image Acquisition and 2D Pose Estimation

Each Jetson Orin Nano runs a camera driver wrapped in a ROS2 node. This node works with cameras supporting the GenICam standard. With our current setup, this node is capable of acquiring images at 22 frames per second. This node continuously publishes the acquired images to a local ROS2 topic. Besides the Image Acquisition ROS2 node, each Jetson Orin Nano is running a 2D pose estimation node. Every time an image is published locally by the node previously described in 4.1, the 2D pose estimation node captures and processes it to perform human detection and keypoint inference. Table 1 shows a comparison between the frame rates of different YOLOv8 models running in our modules.

Figure 3 shows samples of pose estimation from each camera in our layout. In our previous implementation, camera pair 1-2 would not have been able to reconstruct the 3D pose of the human. Our new implementation complements the lack of detection in camera 2 with the detection of cameras 3 and 4.

The improvement on human detection in the cell was quantified for our setup. The robotic cell was divided in a grid with a cell size of 50cm by 50cm. Two approaches were used to identify cells where human detection was possible. First, we tested the implementation as done previously by [6], for each pair of cameras. Afterwards, we tested our implementation for all 4 cameras. The results are presented in Table 2. This experiment was repeated with two subjects, achieving an average result of 69% with our implementation.

Table 1. YOLOv8 Model Comparison

Model	Frame Rate ¹ (<i>fps</i>)	<i>mAP</i> ₅₀ ²	Parameters ²
YOLOv8s-pose	22	86.2	11.6M
YOLOv8m-pose	22	88.8	26.4M
YOLOv8l-pose	19	90.0	44.4M

¹ Frames per second achieved in our module, using an input size of 512x320.

² As reported in Ultralytics.

Fig. 3. Example of pose estimation on a four camera system.

4.2 3D Pose Estimation

On a 30hz frequency, the central PC reads the latest pose information received from every connected edge device. The 2D pose coordinates are identified and stored separately according to the unique ROS2 topic they are being sent through, which corresponds to the camera they generate from. This information is processed as explained in Section 3.2.

The ROS2 implementation processes the final list of triangulations per frame and inserts it into a custom ROS2 message and published. Despite processing the information received from up to four edge devices, the algorithm running in the central PC steadily achieves 30 fps.

5 Conclusions and Future Work

This paper addressed two issues related to vision human tracking in industrial applications: occlusions and scalability. It detailed the implementation of a multi-view camera system, as opposed to a single-view system, to significantly reduce human detection losses when moving around a robotic cell. Additionally, the research showed how the development of edge modules enables the system to run at near real-time speed. Lastly, since the bottleneck is not on the central PC, the paper demonstrated the possibility of scaling the system to even more devices, increasing the detection area of our current setup.

Future work will focus on improving the performance in image acquisition and 2D human pose estimation. Additionally, the calibration procedure for the

Table 2. Percentage of Detected Surface Area

Subjects	Cameras Used						All
	1, 2	1,3	1,4	2,3	2,4	3,4	
<i>A</i>	21.31	42.62	40.98	18.03	27.87	39.34	70.49
<i>B</i>	24.59	50.82	47.54	27.87	31.15	52.46	67.21

cameras can be improved to streamline the implementation of these systems in industrial scenarios and increase their robustness.

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